

Return

ADITYA BIKRAM MISHRA

*Mind flies,
leaving behind the body.*

*Looking back—
a listless form
resting in the lap
of Mother Earth.*

*Joy and happiness,
sorrow and despair,
rise and fall,
high and low—
all now silent.*

*Dear Mother,
I return to you
not as myself,
but as the form
you once gave me—
torn,*

*weathered,
wilted by the road.*

Yet I took nothing from you.

*You let me wander freely,
fearless,
undeterred,
through unknown paths
and distant horizons.*

The treasures were never mine to keep.

*I place them now
at your feet.*

*Bless those
whom you choose
to receive them.*

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